

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT LEARNING IN MUSIC EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This thesis covers the theoretical and methodological foundations of organizing independent learning in the process of music education. It analyzes the content and essence of independent learning, its forms, means, and conditions for effective organization based on the characteristics of music disciplines. It also substantiates the possibilities of forming musical thinking, creative activity, self-development, and professional competencies in students through independent learning.

Introduction.

In today's education system, the traditional model of providing knowledge is changing, and the internal need of a person to learn, the desire for self-development and the ability to act independently are becoming one of the main criteria. Especially in an era of globalization, a sharp increase in the flow of information and the deep penetration of digital technologies into the educational process, the urgency of the transition from a "teacher-centered" approach to a "learner-centered" approach has increased. In such conditions, independent learning is manifested not only as an activity in the form of additional classes or homework, but also as a planned, purposeful and controlled pedagogical process serving the personal and professional development of the learner. Music education, by its nature, relies on creative and practical activities. Such qualities as musical perception, hearing, sense of rhythm, performance technique, artistic thinking and aesthetic taste are formed simultaneously in the combination of both theoretical and practical training. Therefore, the role of independent learning in music is not limited to the consolidation of simple knowledge: it enriches the student's musical experience, opens the way for personal creative research, activates mechanisms for understanding and developing their own potential. For example, independent listening and analysis of a melody, comparison of performance samples, independent practice of reading and singing notes, selection of repertoire, analysis of the quality of performance through audio-video recordings, significantly enhance the student's musical literacy and performing culture. However, the effective organization of independent learning in the process of music education is not a spontaneous process. It requires a clear pedagogical basis, goals, tasks and mechanisms. First of all, the content of independent learning should correspond to the learning outcomes of music, be differentiated taking into account the age-psychological characteristics, level of preparation and individual abilities of the student. Also, if independent work is not based on the principle of systematicity, consistency and gradual complexity, it

becomes fragmentary, that is, random activity. In this case, independent learning is not a responsibility for the student, but can lead to fatigue and a decrease in motivation. From this point of view, the teacher's responsibility in organizing independent learning increases even more: he should be a teacher who is not a controller, but a guide, an adviser, a formator of motivation and a manager of the reflection process. That is, the teacher designs tasks for independent learning in a purposeful manner, arouses interest through creative tasks, and establishes assessment and analysis based on specific criteria. Especially in musical activities, since the result is often manifested in the form of a visible product - performance, melody, composition, improvisation, evaluation criteria must be developed not only on the principle of "right or wrong", but also on the basis of indicators such as artistic expression, rhythm, intonation, timbre, dynamics, and interpretation.

In modern conditions, digital resources and innovative technologies play a special role in increasing the effectiveness of independent learning. Audio and video lessons, virtual piano applications, note reading programs, metronome and tuner applications, the ability to organize the practice process and analyze performance errors through online platforms expand the scope of independent learning. However, it is important to remember that technology is not a goal, but a means: if the pedagogical goal is not clearly defined, digital tools can lead the learner not to study, but to distraction. Therefore, within the pedagogical foundations of independent learning, methodological instructions, time planning, control-reflection mechanisms, incentive methods, and a feedback system play an important role. Thus, the issue of organizing independent learning in music education should be considered not only as a didactic task, but also as a pedagogical problem inextricably linked with the aesthetic and creative development of the individual. This thesis aims to shed light on the pedagogical foundations of this problem, to substantiate the conditions for the effective organization of independent learning, and to put forward methodological proposals suitable for the practice of music education.

Discussion.

The issue of organizing independent learning in music education is currently being interpreted not only as a technical problem related to the redistribution of the curriculum or the reduction of classroom lessons, but as an important pedagogical process aimed at the comprehensive development of the individual. During the discussion, it is determined that independent learning demonstrates its real pedagogical effectiveness only when it is organized in an inextricable link with the content and methodological features of music education.

First of all, the uniqueness of independent learning in music education is that it requires creative and practical activity rather than the reproductive assimilation of knowledge. In the process of studying music, a student does not just memorize theoretical concepts, but also learns them through practical performance, listening, analysis and interpretation. Therefore, the tasks given in the process of independent learning should also be creative in nature, encouraging the student to active musical activity. For example, independently working on a melody, comparing performance options, analyzing the interpretation of a piece by different performers forms the student's ability to think musically and aesthetically evaluate.

The discussions show that the effectiveness of independent learning directly depends on the pedagogical approach. If independent work is given only at the level of "homework", without clear instructions and methodological guidelines, then it will not lead to the development of the student's creative activity, but to mechanical exercises. On the contrary, when independent learning is organized on the basis of a systematic, purposeful and reflexive approach, the student acquires the skills to analyze his own activities, understand his mistakes and eliminate them. This process is an important factor in the formation of a musical performance culture.

Also, independent learning is one of the most effective means of implementing an individual approach in music education. Since each student has different musical abilities, hearing levels, rhythmic abilities, and performance potential, teaching everyone at the same pace within the framework of classroom training does not always produce the expected results. Independent learning, on the other hand, allows the student to work at a pace that suits his or her abilities, practice complex aspects repeatedly, and build a personal repertoire. This is a practical expression of a differentiated and person-centered approach to music education.

Another important aspect of the discussion is the issue of motivation in independent learning. In music education, if internal motivation, that is, interest in art and aesthetic need are not strong, the effectiveness of independent learning decreases. Therefore, the teacher should widely use motivating methods, creative tasks, and reflective assessment methods in the process of independent learning. Recognizing the student's small achievements, discussing the performance process, and expressing constructive feedback ensure the continuity of independent learning.

In modern pedagogical discussions, the role of digital technologies in independent learning is also seen as an important issue. Audio and video recordings, online platforms, and music applications make it possible to organize independent learning more conveniently and effectively. However, the discussion shows that technologies do not improve the quality of education by themselves. They give positive results only if they serve a pedagogical goal. Otherwise, technological tools can lead to superficial activity, not to the development of musical thinking. Therefore, the use of innovative tools in independent learning should also be scientifically based and methodically well-planned.

The results of the discussion show that the process of organizing independent learning in music education is a complex, multifaceted and continuous pedagogical activity. It requires a creative approach, taking into account individual capabilities, supporting motivation, and combining modern pedagogical and technological tools. Only when these factors are combined will independent learning serve to improve the quality of music education and develop the professional and creative competencies of students.

Analysis of the literature on the topic.

The issue of organizing independent learning in music education has been studied by representatives of different eras and scientific schools as a scientific problem formed at the intersection of pedagogy, didactics, and musicology. The analysis of the literature shows that although the concept of independent learning was initially covered as a general pedagogical

category, later it began to have separate scientific interpretations based on the nature of the disciplines, including in the context of music education.

In the scientific works of scientists of our republic, the issue of independent learning was studied mainly in connection with the development of individual-oriented education, a competency-based approach and creative activity. In particular, in the works of scientists such as R. H. Jo'rayev, N. A. Muslimov, U. I. Inoyatov, independent learning was justified as a pedagogical mechanism that increases the cognitive activity of the learner and serves self-development. In research on music education, the scientific works of R. A. Abdullayev, Sh. M. Ganiyeva, O. A. Matyokubov are of particular importance. These studies emphasize the role of independent training in music disciplines in the formation of performing skills, musical thinking and aesthetic taste. However, it can be observed that in these works, independent learning is covered more as a practical exercise, and its foundations as a holistic pedagogical system are not sufficiently systematized.

In foreign scientific literature, the issue of independent learning has been widely studied through the concepts of "self-directed learning", "independent learning" and "autonomous learning". In particular, M. Knowles interprets independent learning as a process related to the ability of a person to plan, implement and evaluate his own educational activities. J. Dewey, justifying the leading role of experience and activity in the educational process, shows independent learning as an important factor in personal development. In foreign research on music education, the works of S. Hallam and K. Swanwick play an important role. They scientifically substantiate the development of musical perception, reflection and creative interpretation through independent studies. Although the pedagogical model, motivational factors and assessment mechanisms of independent learning are developed relatively deeply in foreign sources, most of them do not sufficiently take into account the context of national musical traditions.

In the studies of CIS scientists, the issue of independent learning is covered more from a didactic and methodological point of view. The theoretical views of V. V. Davydov, L. S. Vygotsky, I. Ya. Lerner allow us to connect independent learning with the concept of developmental education. In the field of music education, B. M. Teplov revealed the psychological foundations of independent activity and practice in the development of musical abilities. Although the stages, levels of complexity and issues of pedagogical control of independent learning are quite well developed in CIS studies, their integration with modern digital technologies is not sufficiently covered. In general, the analysis of the literature shows that the issue of independent learning in music education has been studied by various scientific schools from different aspects. However, the issue of organizing independent learning in the process of music education as an integral pedagogical system, in accordance with national and modern requirements, remains relevant. It is this circumstance that determines the scientific validity of the choice of this topic and requires the development of new methodological and pedagogical approaches.

Conclusion.

The results of the theoretical analysis and scientific discussions show that the effective organization of independent learning in music education is an important pedagogical factor that serves not only to strengthen the knowledge and skills of students, but also to develop

their musical thinking, creative activity and professional competencies. Independent learning demonstrates its true didactic and educational significance only when it is organized in harmony with the practical and creative characteristics of music disciplines.

It can be concluded that in the process of organizing independent learning, the clarity of the pedagogical goal, the systematicity and consistency of tasks, taking into account the individual capabilities of learners, and the presence of reflection and assessment mechanisms are of great importance. In particular, the creative nature of independent activities in musical activities has a positive effect on the formation of students' aesthetic taste, performance culture, and the need for self-development.

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